

Identification of Protease Producing Thermophilic Bacteria from Medang River Hot Springs, Jambi with 16S rRNA Gene Analysis

Fanny Zulkhairiah (1810422027), Biology Department, Mathematic and Science Faculty, Andalas University, Padang.

Microbial life is very interesting to study further. Along with the development of science, more interesting things have been found related to microbial life. One of them is thermophilic bacteria that are able to live in hot water and produce certain enzymes such as proteases that can be used in various sectors such as the industrial sector. The reason I choose this topic as a literature review is because I want to study further about the thermophilic bacteria that produce protease enzymes found in hot springs of the Medang River, Jambi and combining it with genetic science for the study of identification of thermophilic bacteria that produce protease enzymes based on 16S rRNA gene analysis.

Thermophilic bacteria are bacteria that are able to live at high temperatures because they are tolerant of extreme environmental temperatures (Akhdiya, 2003). Thermophilic bacteria can be divided into three groups, obligate thermophilic, facultative thermophilic, and extreme thermophilic. Obligate thermophilic have a temperature range of 65°-70°C, facultative thermophilic have a temperature range of 50°-65°C, and extreme thermophilic have a temperature range of more than 70°C. Strain *Bacillus coagulans* is an example of an obligate thermophilic group, strain *Bacillus stearothermophilus* is an example of a facultative thermophilic group and *Bacillus caldolyticus* and *Thermus thermophiles* are examples of an extreme thermophilic group (Friedman, 1992).

Thermophilic bacteria are capable in converting certain enzymes that are stable to heat, one of which is the production of proteases that are useful in various industrial sectors such as the food industry and biotechnology (Akhdiya, 2003). Protease enzymes are also applied in the textile industry, protein hydrolysis, milk processing, medicine, fermented drinks and sewage (Moon & Parulekar, 1993). The resistance of this enzyme in hot temperature makes it have a very high commercial value (Agustien, 2010). Indonesia has various types of protease producing thermophilic bacteria, so it is hoped that it will be possible to produce domestic protease enzymes in the future (Wahyuna, Agustien & Periadnadi, 2012). According to Wahyuna, Agustien & Periadnadi (2012), the hot springs of the Medang River have temperatures ranging from 50°C to 78°C. with a pH between 8,45 to 8,71 which means alkaline. Based on the research, it was found that 39 isolates of thermophilic bacteria that produced protease enzymes had the highest proteolytic index of 7,89 mm and the highest protease enzyme activity of 13,592 U/ml. Based on the characterization of thermo proteolytic bacteria, one of the isolates was gram positive, rod-shaped cells and non-motile. According to research by Firliani, Agustien, & Febria (2015), they found 28 isolates of thermophilic bacteria and 10 of them have potential to produce protease enzymes with a proteolytic index between 0,27-3,89.

The most widely used DNA based molecular detection method is the Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) which is an exponential increase in DNA fragments using enzymes in vitro (Durmawati, 2019) to identify protease producing thermophilic bacteria. PCR analysis

of the 16S rRNA gene is used because, according to Faradiska (2012), the use of the 16S rRNA gene has the advantage that its properties don't change over a long period of time and have a small mutation rate. The work step of the gene analysis method of 16S rRNA is DNA isolation with kit Invitrogen, DNA amplification by PCR with primary set of 16S rRNA and then phylogenetic analysis (Sayuti, Siregar, Amin, Agustien, & Djamaan, 2018). Phylogenetic analysis was carried out by analyzing the results of bacterial DNA sequencing and matched with the available data on the Gene Bank Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) on NCBI (Japri, Sulistyanyingtyas, Darmawati, & Ethica, 2019).

Colony of protease producing thermophilic bacteria in hot springs of the Medang River, Jambi has been isolated and characterized by macroscopic observations and several isolates have been obtained with special characteristics, but we still don't know for sure the name of the genus and species of the isolate. By using molecular identification of bacteria we can find out the name of the genus and species of the protease producing thermophilic bacteria more accurately.

Bibliography

- Akhdiya, A. (2003). *Isolasi Bakteri Penghasil Enzim Protease Alkalin Termotabil. Balai Penelitian Bioteknologi & Sumberdaya Genetik Pertanian*. Bogor.
- Agustien, A. (2010). *Isolasi, Optimasi & Amobilisasi Brevibacillus agri A-03 dari Sumber Air Panas Sumatera Barat Penghasil Protease Alkali & Keratinase Termotabil Serta Aplikasinya*. Padjadjaran University, Bandung.
- Darmawati, S. (2019). *Monograf: Sistematika Polifasik Untuk Deteksi Keanekaragaman Genetik Salmonella typhi*. Yogyakarta: ED I. Salma Idea.
- Faradiska, W. (2012). *Isolasi dan Karakterisasi Bakteri Endofit dari Akar Tanaman Kentang (Solamun tuberosum) Menggunakan Primer Penanda RAPD*. Maulana Malik Ibrahim University, Malang.
- Firliani, W., Agustien, A., & Febria, F.A. (2015). Karakterisasi Bakteri Termofilik Penghasil Enzim Protease Netral. *Jurnal Biologi Universitas Andalas*, 4(1), 9-14.
- Friedman, M. S. (1992). *Thermophilic Microorganism. Encyclopedia of Microbiology*(Vol. 4). New York: Academic Press, Inc.
- Japri, N. A., Sulistyanyingtyas, A.R., Darmawati, S., & Ethica, N.S. (2019). Isolasi dan Identifikasi Molekular Bakteri Proteolitik *Staphylococcus cohnii* Strain IRLV5 pada Rusip Udang Putih (*Litopeaneus Vannamei*) Pasca Fermentasi 120 Jam Berdasarkan Analisis Gen 16s rRNA. *Prosiding Mahasiswa Seminar Nasional Unimus*, 2, 325-333.
- Moon, S. H., and Parulekar, S. J. (1993). Some Observation on Protease Producing in Continuous Suspension Cultures of *Bacillus firmus*. *Biotechnol. Bioeng*, 41(1), 43-54.
- Sayuti, I., Siregar, Y.I., Amin, B., Agustien, A., & Djamaan, A., (2018). Identification of Bacterial Hydrocarbonoplastic in Waste Tanks, Patapahan, Riau, Indonesia, using 16s rRNA. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, 12(2), 671-677.
- Wahyuna, D., Agustien, A., & Periadnadi. (2012). Isolasi dan Karakterisasi Bakteri Termo Proteolitik Sumber Air Panas Sungai Medang, Sungai Penuh, Jambi. *Jurnal Biologi Universitas Andalas*, 1(2), 93-98.